

Reservoir Computing in Real-World Environments: Optimizing the Cost of Offline and Online Training

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Abstract—The remarkable success of attention-based models in real-world applications has sparked a crucial question for Reservoir Computing (RC): Can its inherent computational efficiency compete with the high-performance, yet energy-intensive, novel deep learning architectures? Can Deep and modular RC neural networks address state-of-the-art challenges in Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing? In the attempt to consolidate RC capabilities towards more complex tasks, this paper delves into the exploration of a comprehensive RC’s offline-online cycle cost analysis. Our investigation highlights hyper-parameters (HPs) optimization as a major bottleneck in RC deployment, particularly for those exploring RC capabilities and those who want to maintain user-level knowledge of the solution. To address this, we introduce an adaptive ϵ -Greedy-based search exploration mechanism, significantly streamlining the off-line optimization process while maintaining high accuracy. Furthermore, we enhance existing RC frameworks to support online transfer learning and inference, enabling seamless, fast, and energy-efficient adaptation to real-world environments. By analyzing the impact of optimized HPs on performance, we aim to demonstrate the viability of RC as a powerful and efficient alternative for many practical applications, including those on devices with limited resources. Experimental results proved that our solution is able to reduce the time required for offline HPs optimization by 70%, enabling energy savings of up to 88%. Moreover, in the online scenario, it guarantees similar performance in terms of accuracy while reducing memory usage by 66%.

Index Terms—Reservoir Computing, Intrinsic Plasticity, Echo State Networks, Energy Efficiency, Artificial Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has undergone transformative advancements in recent years, with attention-based models [1] emerging as a cornerstone of modern AI due to their exceptional performance in real-world applications. Today, state-of-the-art (SotA) standards are dominated by Large Language Models (LLMs) with agent-based solutions [2] and Computer Vision Transformers [3], setting a high benchmark that any new approach must surpass. These advancements have redefined the landscape of AI, pushing the boundaries of what is achievable and establishing a new paradigm for innovation and competition in the field. However, these advancements come at a significant computational and energy cost [4], prompting a renewed interest in alternative and greener paradigms like brain-inspired machine learning. Among those solutions, Reservoir Computing (RC) [5] is celebrated for its computational efficiency [6] and simplicity, and it has demonstrated

potential across a broad spectrum of applications. However, its scalability and adaptability to complex and dynamic environments remains underexplored. In fact, despite its clear advantage in computational efficiency, the lack of a standardized training methodology presents a significant barrier to its broader adoption by other research communities.

This paper examines the actual cost of RC offline-online cycle as a critical factor in determining its practical applicability to SotA computer science challenges. Firstly, we highlight the non-trivial nature of hyper-parameters (HPs) optimization in RC due to its intrinsic dynamics operating at the edge of chaos [7]. Secondly, we investigate on the HPs selection generalization from an offline controlled environment to an online with unpredictable and evolving dynamics. Our goal is to provide tools for positioning RC as a competitive alternative in the era of resource-intensive AI models. Addressing this complexity is essential to establish RC as a viable and efficient solution for modern energy-efficient AI applications, particularly as deep [8], [9] and modular [10], [11] RC architectures have to be considered to meet the escalating demands of users for high-performance AI systems to solve complex problems. By analyzing the influence of optimized HPs on RC’s performance, we aim to establish its potential as a scalable and efficient solution for practical AI applications, effectively bridging the gap between computational efficiency and real-world utility.

Building on remarkable contributions from the RC research community, this paper focuses on two primary contributions:

- 1) A novel **ϵ -Greedy strategy** for RC HPs search, offering a systematic approach to identify optimal configurations efficiently.
- 2) An **extension of ReservoirPy** [12] to support Intrinsic Plasticity for online training and forecasting, enhancing RC’s adaptability and performance in dynamic environments.

Our work introduces a memory-assisted search exploration mechanism that reduces the computational overhead associated with HPs tuning by the 70% of the time and up to the 88% of energy. Furthermore, we extend RC’s capabilities to encompass online transfer learning and inference, enabling seamless adaptation to real-world scenarios, achieving less than a 1% accuracy drop compared to offline performance

using only 33% of the memory needed by a benchmark solution. The paper is organized as follows: Section II provides background on RC and HP optimization, while Section III outlines the motivations and methodology. Section IV details the proposed offline HP optimization approach, followed by an analysis of results and online learning in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes with key remarks and future directions.

II. BACKGROUND

Reservoir Computing [13] is a computational framework originally designed for temporal/sequential data processing. It consists of a reservoir for mapping inputs into a high-dimensional space and a readout for pattern analysis from the high-dimensional states in the reservoir.

A. RC and Echo State Networks

Formally, a Reservoir Computing model consists of three main components:

- **Input Layer:** Maps the input signal $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_u}$ into a higher-dimensional state space.
- **Reservoir (Recurrent Nonlinear System):** A high-dimensional dynamical system with fixed random connections, where the state $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ evolves according to:

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = f(\mathbf{W}_{\text{in}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}(t)) \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_u}$ is the input weight matrix,
- $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_x}$ is the reservoir weight matrix,
- $f(\cdot)$ is a nonlinear activation function (e.g., tanh).
- **Readout Layer:** A trainable linear mapping from the reservoir states to the output $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y}$, defined as:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{W}_{\text{out}}\mathbf{x}(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y \times N_x}$ is the only trainable parameter, usually optimized via linear regression.

The **Echo State Property (ESP)** [14] is the fundamental condition to ensure the stability and computational effectiveness of RC models, particularly Echo State Networks (ESNs). It guarantees that the influence of initial conditions on the reservoir states vanishes over time, allowing the system to produce stable and reproducible responses to input sequences.

Formally, the Echo State Property is satisfied if, for any two initial states $\mathbf{x}_1(0)$ and $\mathbf{x}_2(0)$, and for the same input sequence $\mathbf{u}(t)$, the state trajectories $\mathbf{x}_1(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}_2(t)$ asymptotically converge:

$$\|\mathbf{x}_1(t) - \mathbf{x}_2(t)\| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow \infty. \quad (3)$$

This ensures that the reservoir dynamics are uniquely determined by the input history, independent of initial conditions.

A sufficient condition for the ESP is that the spectral radius $\rho(\mathbf{W})$ of the reservoir weight matrix \mathbf{W} satisfies:

$$\rho(\mathbf{W}) < 1. \quad (4)$$

This constraint ensures that perturbations in the reservoir states decay over time, leading to stable and well-behaved dynamics.

B. Intrinsic Plasticity

Building upon this ESP, **Intrinsic Plasticity (IP)**, a concept derived from neuroscience [15], allows individual neurons within the reservoir to autonomously adjust their firing rates in response to input, enhancing the network's ability to adapt and learn from its environment without the need for external supervision. As a result, the synaptic weights of a network are modified based on the intrinsic activity of the neurons, rather than external teaching signals.

In the context of RC, intrinsic plasticity [16] can be modeled by modifying the neuron dynamics to optimize their firing rates. Let the state of a neuron at time t be denoted by $x(t)$, and its desired firing rate is θ . The update rule for intrinsic plasticity can be expressed as:

$$\tau \frac{dx(t)}{dt} = -x(t) + f(W \cdot x(t)) + \gamma(\theta - |x(t)|), \quad (5)$$

where:

- $x(t)$: State of the neuron at time t ,
- τ : Time constant controlling the neuron's dynamics,
- W : Weight matrix of the network that connects neurons,
- $f(\cdot)$: Activation function that determines the output based on the neuron's state,
- γ : Scaling factor that controls the strength of the plasticity,
- θ : Target firing rate for the neuron,
- $|x(t)|$: Absolute value of the neuron's state, which represents its firing rate.

The goal of IP is to modify the neuronal activity such that the firing rate of each neuron converges to the desired rate θ . This form of self-regulation enhances the network's ability to learn from the temporal characteristics of the input signal. IP-based RC is particularly well-suited for resource-constrained edge devices [5], owing to the minimal computational overhead required for training and the technology's ability to adapt in real-time to new data distributions.

C. ESNs Applications

Several emerging solutions have already taken advantage of RC's ability to adaptively learn spatiotemporal features and hidden patterns in complex time series, e.g., signal classification, non-linear time series prediction, dynamic control, and partial differential equations solving [6]. ESNs, one of the most extensively studied frameworks in RC, have recently been extended to improve their memory capacity for time series prediction, as in the Residual ESN (ResESN) [17]. Considering speech-recognition applications, hierarchical-task reservoir (HTR) is significantly performant and extremely efficient with respect to baseline LSTM-based approaches [8]. The ESNs have also demonstrated significant potential in image processing and computer vision tasks. In colour image segmentation, ESNs were utilized as feature extractors

for blood vessel segmentation applications, reaching state-of-the-art performance in accuracy and reducing the inference time [18]. Multi-Reservoir ESN (MRESN) [19] improves benchmarks by processing the entire image in independent reservoirs working in parallel, enabling a reduction of training and testing times, and significantly lowering memory requirements. ESNs have also been integrated with Liquid Neural Networks (LNNs) in a hybrid framework for real-time object detection in autonomous vehicles, enhancing the balance between precision and inference speed [20].

D. HPs Search

Regarding HPs search, grid search remains the most widely used approach across various applications, ranging from canonical ESNs [21]–[23] to distributed and federated architectures [24]. A first tentative to support HPs search in a more optimized way has been carried out in [25], where random search has proven to sample more efficiently than grid search. In fact, grid search guarantees discretized maps with gradients of performance depending on your HPs. However, grid search probably misses some of the best performances and has a high computational time cost. Similarly, [26] provides a stochastic optimization technique for hyperparameter tuning for hardware RC implementations, where only partial or even lack of knowledge regarding the reservoir’s feedback weights prevents smarter guided solutions.

III. MOTIVATIONS AND METHODOLOGY

Machine learning pipelines are essential for deploying data-driven solutions in real-world applications. In industrial settings, MLOps (Machine Learning Operations) streamlines the process of bringing these solutions to market, borrowing principles from DevOps, and applying continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) practices to machine learning models. Driven by the need of reducing the development and maintenance costs as much as possible in the long run, these practices ensure a smooth transition from development to testing and finally to production, mirroring the robust workflows used for traditional software development. With the same idea in mind, academia models time-dependent changes in data distribution and learning objectives [27] trying to generalize training mechanisms towards the fundamental goal of AI: developing stable algorithms capable of adapting to real-world scenarios rather than relying on pre-defined solutions for every conceivable task.

Figure 1 illustrates the CI/CD-inspired workflow of RC model development and deployment, highlighting offline and online phases. In the offline phase, data preprocessing, hyperparameter tuning, model training, and validation occur in a controlled environment. The online phase involves real-time data processing, model adaptation, and forecasting. In this study, we focus on **Hyperparameter Search** in the offline phase, as well as **Model Adaptation** and **Forecasting** in the online phase. Specifically, we investigate the application of an RC model to a different dataset with a similar distribution while maintaining the HPs identified in the controlled offline

Fig. 1: Deployment of the RC solution in real-world scenarios. The red blocks emphasize the key focus of this study.

environment. To achieve this, we conduct offline HPs validation using batch processing on an edge server with enhanced computational capabilities. In what follows, we present our proposal for the HPs search and the model adaptation and forecasting together with their background information.

A. HPs Search

Despite the significant advancements discussed in Section II, the inherently chaotic nature of RC poses challenges to its broader interdisciplinary adoption and further innovation by expert data scientists. In particular, the selection of HPs has a profound impact on model performance, often discouraging new users from exploring RC’s potential on custom datasets. Without sufficient domain knowledge, tuning these parameters can result in an extensive and costly search process, ultimately offsetting RC’s advantage of shorter training times. Consequently, when transitioning from a familiar problem to a new one, consolidated HPs may require additional tuning, further complicating the optimization process and the final deployment of the model in an online and real-world setting. Moreover, when RC is treated as an atomic component that can be integrated with other technologies—such as Convolutional Neural Networks for computer vision tasks—or combined with multiple instances of itself in stacked, deep or grouped architectures [28], [29], the process of HPs selection becomes computationally prohibitive. The interaction between such a powerful yet inherently stochastic feature extraction mechanism and other computational modules is not straightforward, especially in cases where intermediate labels are unavailable or fail to correspond to real-world representations (e.g., latent space embeddings). In such scenarios, identifying which part of the architecture is underperforming would necessitate extensive trial-and-error iterations. This likely explains why composite RC architectures proposed in the SotA often employ similar—or even identical—hyperparameters across their constituent modules even when abstract representations are characterized by different data distributions, as in [8].

While the complexity of a task or the heterogeneity within training data can offer valuable insights into reasonable HPs to explore, this approach is not always feasible. This is due to the inherently time-varying nature of real-world scenarios, as well as the nuanced, experience-driven expertise of human operators. On the one hand, it is true that existing remarkable frameworks, particularly ReservoirPy¹, greatly facilitate the adoption and validation of RC; but on the other hand, many of the established practices for HP optimization still rely heavily on manual and iterative interventions. While these frameworks provide essential tools for implementation and experimentation, they often fall short of fully automating the optimization process, leaving significant room for human-driven refinement and decision-making. To fill this gap, we propose a novel HP search solution based on an ϵ -greedy approach designed for balancing the exploration of new parameters configuration and exploiting the known successful ones. Section IV provides the details of the proposed HP search solution.

B. Model Adaptation and Forecasting

Another critical factor to consider when selecting optimal HPs is their ability to generalize from an offline, controlled environment to an online, real-world setting. HPs tuned under controlled conditions may not always perform effectively when deployed in dynamic, real-world scenarios, where data distributions, noise levels, and operational constraints can vary significantly. This discrepancy highlights the importance of ensuring that HPs are not only optimized for theoretical or simulated performance but also robust enough to adapt to the unpredictable and evolving nature of real-world applications. To enhance the online applicability of RC, we build upon existing solutions to implement Intrinsic Plasticity in an online manner—an approach not natively supported by ReservoirPy. Specifically, we extend [16], integrating a Recursive Least Squares (RLS) filter [30]. The resulting module dynamically adjusts RC’s internal connections based on the evolving data distribution while performing regression sample by sample. Section V-C presents the corresponding empirical results, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach.

IV. ϵ -GREEDY RC FOR HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Facilitating the application of RC across diverse domains hinges significantly on effective HPs tuning, which is essential for achieving robust and reliable performance. However, identifying optimal HPs is often a computationally demanding task that necessitates a delicate balance between exploring new configurations and exploiting known successful ones. This balance is particularly crucial given constraints such as limited energy and time budgets. Without careful management, the optimization process risks either becoming trapped in suboptimal configurations or excessively exploring the search space, even after discovering configurations that are close to optimal. Striking this balance is therefore key to ensuring efficient and effective HPs tuning in real-world applications.

¹<https://github.com/reservoirpy>

Algorithm 1: ϵ -Greedy Hyperparameter Search for Reservoir Computing with Fixed Hyperparameters and a Penalty for Large Reservoir Sizes

Input: Training data (X_{train}, y_{train}) , Test data (X_{test}, y_{test}) , Number of iterations n_{iter} , Exploration parameter ϵ , Categorical HPs Θ_c , Uniformly distributed hyperparameters Θ_u , Log-uniformly distributed hyperparameters Θ_{log} , Reservoir size parameter θ_{size} , Hyperparameter to fix: $hp_{fix} \in \{IS, SR, LR\}$

Output: Optimal HPs θ^*

Initialize

search history $\mathcal{H} = \emptyset$

memory buffer $\mathcal{M} = \emptyset$

best score $S^* \leftarrow -\infty$

for $i = 1$ to n_{iter} **do**

if $\mathcal{M} \neq \emptyset$ and $rand() > \epsilon$ **then**

 Select base configuration θ_b from \mathcal{M} ;

 Generate new parameters $\theta \sim P(\theta_b)$ with perturbations;

end

else

 Sample θ from prior distributions::

if $hp_{fix} \in \{IS, SR, LR\}$ **then**

 Fix $\theta_{hp_{fix}}$; vary others;

end

$\theta_c \sim P(\Theta_c)$ for categorical HPs;

$\theta_u \sim U(\Theta_u)$ for uniform HPs;

$\theta_{log} \sim \text{LogUniform}(\Theta_{log})$ for log-uniform HPs;

end

 reservoir_size = θ_{size} ;

 penalty_factor = f(reservoir_size);

$S = \text{Evaluate}(\theta, X_{train}, y_{train}, X_{test}, y_{test}) -$
penalty factor;

 Append (θ, S) to history \mathcal{H} ;

if $S > S^*$ **then**

$S^* \leftarrow S, \theta^* \leftarrow \theta$;

 Append θ to memory \mathcal{M} ;

end

end

return θ^*, S^*

To address this challenge, we propose an efficient algorithm that leverages a ϵ -Greedy inspired exploration of the HPs optimization problem [31], [32]. This method intelligently navigates the HPs search space by employing an ϵ -Greedy RC strategy, which dynamically balances exploration and exploitation. The algorithm maintains a history of evaluated configurations and a memory buffer to store the k-top most promising hyperparameter sets, ensuring a systematic and adaptive search optimization process. This approach is designed to offer a

versatile and generalizable framework for HPs exploration, making it a powerful tool for RC applicability to various datasets, environments, and tasks of varying complexity levels.

Algorithm 1 formally describes our approach to hyperparameter search for RC. By maintaining a history of evaluated HPs and a memory buffer storing the most promising configurations, the algorithm either perturbs a previously successful configuration (exploitation) by adding Gaussian noise to the values or samples a new set of HPs from a predefined search space, prioritizing smaller reservoir sizes in the reward function and encouraging exploration.

Additionally, as suggested in [25], certain hyperparameters, such as Input Scaling (IS), Spectral Radius (SR), and Leak Rate (LR), are fixed one at a time during the search to avoid conflicting interdependencies. The selected configuration is then evaluated on training and test data, yielding a performance score. If the new configuration outperforms the current best, it updates the best-known parameters and adds them to memory. This iterative process continues for a fixed number of iterations, ultimately returning the optimal HPs set identified during the search. By prioritizing the search for smaller configurations, we drastically reduce the computational resources and time required for HP optimization on a wide range of configurations. This approach not only enhances efficiency but also aligns with practical constraints such as limited energy budgets and the need for faster deployment in real-world applications. Section V-A empirically identifies the optimal ϵ value across the two different datasets we have used to validate our approach.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Setup and Preliminaries

To evaluate the performance, we chose to explore a broad range of HPs to cover scenarios where domain and/or technological knowledge may be lacking. Table I outlines the range of values for each hyperparameter in the context of a single IPReservoir unit, which refers to a reservoir computing model enhanced with intrinsic plasticity mechanisms to improve adaptability and learning efficiency. Notably, as initially suggested in [13] and further discussed in [25], we model some HPs using a logarithmic distribution instead of a uniform distribution, as this approach has been shown to more effectively cover the hyperparameter search space. For our experiments, we used a virtual machine hosted on Azure² as the edge server. It is powered by an AMD EPYC 7763 64-Core Processor, based on the x86_64 architecture with support for both 32-bit and 64-bit operations. The system is configured with 32 CPU cores, approximately 128 GB of RAM, and operates without GPU acceleration. The overall cost of using this infrastructure as a service (IaaS) is approximately 1'000 USD per month.

For the forecasting task, we employed an IPReservoir Computing unit to predict the next time step ($t+1$) on two distinct

TABLE I: Hyperparameter search space for the Reservoir Computing (RC) model.

Hyperparameter	Search Space
Number of Units	{5, 50, 500, 5000} (Log-uniform)
IP Epochs	{10, 100, 1000} (Log-uniform)
Transient Duration	{10, 100, 1000} (Discrete)
Seed	12345 (Fixed)
N Trials	30 (Fixed)
Spectral Radius	$[10^{-2}, 10^1]$ (Log-uniform)
Input Scaling	$[10^{-5}, 2 \times 10^2]$ (Log-uniform)
Learning Rate	$[10^{-5}, 10^{-2}]$ (Log-uniform)
Ridge	$[10^{-8}, 10^1]$ (Log-uniform)
Mu	[0, 1] (Linear-uniform)
Connectivity	[0.1, 0.5] (Linear-uniform)
Activation	{“sigmoid”, “tanh”} (Categorical)

datasets: the UCI Occupancy Detection dataset [33] and the Beijing Multi-Site Air Quality dataset [34].

The **Occupancy Detection** dataset presents a relatively simple classification task, aiming to predict whether an office room is occupied based on sensor data such as light, temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels. In the original study, statistical models like Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and Random Forest (RF) achieved high prediction accuracies ranging from 95% to 99%. The dataset is relatively straightforward, as occupancy is highly correlated with CO₂ levels and temperature. For instance, using only temperature as a predictor, LDA achieved 85% and 83% accuracy on two test sets, demonstrating that even a single sensor input can yield reasonable results under specific conditions.

The **Beijing Multi-Site Air Quality** dataset, on the other hand, represents a significantly more complex forecasting challenge. It comprises air-quality monitoring data collected from 36 locations across Beijing between March 2010 and February 2017. The dataset includes six hourly observed meteorological variables: air temperature, wind direction and speed, pressure, relative humidity (or dew point temperature), precipitation, and PM_{2.5} concentrations. Even state-of-the-art LSTM-based models [35], [36] achieved only 93% accuracy and an R^2 score, highlighting the intricate and dynamic nature of air quality prediction.

As a preliminary study, we validate our assumptions about higher impact on HP search exploration using Optuna [37]. Figure 2 illustrates the importance of HPs in two different contexts: one where the impact on hyperparameter search duration is not considered, and another where it is considered alongside the objective function. For the occupancy dataset, when duration is not considered, “Mu” and “Connectivity” are the most influential HPs with importance scores of 32% and 15%, respectively. However, when duration is factored in, “Units” becomes significantly more important with a score of 66%, while “IP Learning Rate” drops to 6%. Similarly, for

²<https://portal.azure.com/>

the air quality dataset, "Input Scaling" and "Units" are the most critical HPs without considering duration, with scores of 45% and 18%, respectively. When duration is considered, "Units" dominates with a score of 78%, and other HPs like "Spectral Radius" and "Input Scaling" see a drastic reduction in importance, both dropping to 0.01. These results highlight how the consideration of search duration can significantly alter the perceived importance of HPs, emphasizing the need to balance optimization efficiency with computational cost.

In addition, we explore how different values of ϵ affect our ϵ -Greedy RC optimizer search time and objective score across the two considered datasets. Figure 3 reports the impact of the ϵ parameter on the objective function scores (F1 for occupancy data and R^2 for air quality data) and training times across different ϵ values. For the occupancy dataset, the F1 scores are consistently high, ranging from 92.59% to 97.19%, indicating that the model's performance is robust across various ϵ values. The highest F1 score of 97.19% is achieved at ϵ values of 10% and 40%. However, the training times vary significantly, with the shortest training time of approximately 30 minutes at ϵ 30% and the longest of about 11 hours at ϵ equal to 10%.

For the Beijing Air Quality Dataset, the R^2 score shows a notable improvement as ϵ increases from 5% to 10%, jumping from 7.26% to 92.69%, and peaking at 94.59% for ϵ 40%. The training times for the air quality dataset also exhibit significant variability, with the longest training time of approximately 38 hours at ϵ 20% and the shortest of less than 6 hours at ϵ 30%. The peak R^2 score at ϵ 40% is achieved with a moderate training time of around 7181 seconds.

Results across the two datasets confirm that while higher values of ϵ do not significantly impact objective function scores on average, this improvement often comes at the cost of increased search time required to explore all trials. On the other hand, shorter values of ϵ may cause the optimizer to get trapped in sub-optimal configurations, limiting its ability to explore the hyperparameter space effectively and therefore resulting in undesirable states. For those reasons, to balance search duration and objective score we then set ϵ to 30% in our experiments. This choice allows for a reasonable exploration of the hyperparameter space while maintaining computational efficiency, ensuring that the optimizer can achieve competitive performance without excessive training times.

B. Hyperparameters Search

In this section, we present the comparison of our ϵ -Greedy RC approach against Optuna Hyperband Pruner and ReservoirPy Random search based on Hyperopt [38]. Specifically, we illustrate the time required for HP search optimizers to explore 30 different trial configurations. While the Optuna Hyperband Pruner employs a Bayesian optimization strategy to select the next configuration, Hyperopt conducts its search in a completely random manner. As a result, Optuna reduces the likelihood of selecting low-performing configurations over time but incurs additional resource and time costs due to the complexity of Bayesian optimization. In contrast, Hyperopt introduces no such overhead. However, its purely random

Fig. 2: HP's importance using Optuna with and without considering search duration on the (a) Occupancy Detection Dataset and the (b) Beijing Air Quality Dataset.

search increases the chances of exploring larger reservoir unit sizes, which are not always optimal and increase the search time.

In Figure 4, for the Occupancy dataset, ϵ -Greedy RC completes the 30 trials in less than 30 minutes, whereas the Optuna Hyperband Pruner and Hyperopt take over five and eight hours, respectively. In terms of F1 score, all optimizers achieve approximately 97%, with Optuna obtaining the highest score by a margin of less than 1%. For the Air Quality dataset, both Optuna and Hyperband achieve an R^2 score of approximately 94%, while ϵ -greedy reaches around 92%. Regarding exploration time, Optuna and Hyperband require about 20 hours to evaluate all selected configurations, whereas ϵ -Greedy RC completes all trials in under 6 hours. Overall, as empirically demonstrated, the overhead introduced by ϵ -Greedy RC has a minimal impact on search time since, by favoring smaller reservoir unit sizes, a more detailed exploration of other HPs is enabled. In this regard, Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of reservoir unit sizes across the two datasets. As shown, ϵ -Greedy RC tests smaller configurations more frequently than the other methods, allowing potential higher objective function scores.

Furthermore, the longer convergence time required by Optuna and Hyperband leads to higher energy consumption. Figure 6 shows that ϵ -greedy reduces energy usage by up to a factor of eight for the Occupancy dataset and nearly five for the Air Quality dataset. Since ϵ -greedy is both more energy-efficient and time-efficient, it can potentially run

Fig. 3: ϵ param exploration on the (a) Occupancy Detection Dataset and the (b) Beijing Air Quality Dataset.

Fig. 4: HP Exploration Timeline for the three optimizers considered in this study across 30 trials on the (a) Occupancy Detection Dataset and the (b) Beijing Air Quality Dataset.

more trials, ultimately achieving comparable performance to the other two methods—which offer slightly better objective function scores—at a significantly higher computational cost. To facilitate reproducibility, the code has been made publicly available in our GitHub repository ³.

C. Online Learning

In this section, we present the results of applying the HPs identified offline to an online scenario. For each dataset, we selected a new portion that was not used during offline training

and further split it into two parts. The first part is used to allow IP to adapt to the new data distribution. Notably, all HPs remain unchanged during this phase, with only the IP gain and bias adjusting dynamically in the transient state. The final trained model is then evaluated on the second portion of the dataset. In this phase, we utilized the ReservoirPy implementation of IPReservoir and extended its functionality by integrating it with our custom RLS filter. This enhancement enables iterative adaptation of the regressor on a sample-by-sample basis. Tables II and III present the objective scores for each HP optimizer for the Occupation and Air Quality

³<https://gitlab.cttc.es/supercom/ijcnn-2025-epsilongreedy-rc>

Fig. 5: Units Size distribution across trials for each optimization strategy on the (a) Occupancy Detection Dataset and the (b) Beijing Air Quality Dataset.

Fig. 6: Total energy consumption of each optimization strategy across the two considered datasets.

datasets, respectively. For each optimizer, we deployed a model instance using the corresponding HPs identified during the offline phase. Additionally, since Optuna’s HPs proved to be the ones with higher objective scores, we used those configurations to compare the canonical offline prediction with our custom implementation.

For the Occupancy dataset (Table II), the offline-online comparison reveals highly similar F1 and Accuracy scores, with final values around 97% and 98%, respectively. Conversely, for the Air Quality dataset (Table III), the online implementation outperforms the offline version, achieving an approximately 6% higher R^2 score and 700 lower MSE. Additionally, in terms of memory usage, Table IV shows that the online implementation requires up to 126MB less than its offline counterpart, enabling a memory savings of 66% and, thus, making it more suitable for constrained environments and mobile devices.

When comparing the generalizability of HPs in a transfer learning setting, the Optuna Hyperband Pruner HPs achieve the highest objective scores on both datasets, demonstrating that on the dataset we considered larger reservoir sizes are better suited for adapting to novel data distributions. In terms of training time, ϵ -Greedy RC requires an order of magnitude less time due to the use of smaller reservoir

TABLE II: Occupancy Detection Dataset

HP Exploration Strategy	F1 Score [%]	Accuracy [%]	Train time [ms]	Prediction time [ms]
Optuna online	97.1 ± 0.05	97.8 ± 0.04	2.928 ± 0.906	$0.789 \pm 5 \times 10^{-2}$
Reservoirpy Hyperopt	96.1 ± 0.00	97.0 ± 0.01	3.084 ± 1.234	$0.991 \pm 6 \times 10^{-2}$
ϵ -Greedy RC	96.1 ± 0.00	97.1 ± 0.00	0.368 ± 0.062	0.347 ± 0.035
Optuna offline	97.1 ± 0.00	97.9 ± 0.00		

TABLE III: Beijing Air Quality Dataset

HP Exploration Strategy	R2 Score [%]	MSE	Train time [ms]	Prediction time [ms]
Optuna online	85.9 ± 0.9	1384.507 ± 84.094	3.441 ± 1.512	$0.0966 \pm 9 \times 10^{-2}$
Reservoirpy Hyperopt	85.8 ± 0.9	1394.923 ± 89.214	3.358 ± 1.427	$0.0909 \pm 9 \times 10^{-2}$
ϵ -Greedy RC	83.7 ± 0.2	1593.139 ± 28.661	0.413 ± 0.104	$0.0381 \pm 1 \times 10^{-1}$
Optuna offline	79.4 ± 0.03	2029 ± 0.3		

TABLE IV: Memory Usage

Modality	Occupancy Detection Dataset [MB]	Beijing Air Quality Dataset [MB]
Offline	190.824	314.772
Online	63.928	214.06
Saved Memory	126.896	100.712

units, along with a roughly three-fold reduction in prediction time. This makes it particularly advantageous for deployment on resource-constrained devices and in online environments where fast adaptation and minimal computational overhead are crucial.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we explored the challenges and opportunities of RC, focusing on the cost of offline and online training. Our goal has been to enable easier deployment of RC solutions for fostering the research for competing with SotA AI applications and for its deployment in real-world settings and resource-constrained devices. We identified HPs optimization as a major bottleneck in RC adoption and proposed an adaptive ϵ -greedy search strategy to significantly reduce the time and energy costs associated with offline tuning. Our approach demonstrated a **70% reduction in optimization time** and up to **88% energy savings**, making RC a more viable solution for resource-constrained edge devices. By consolidating HPs search with an empirical study, we propose an ϵ -Greedy-inspired strategy tailored to the unique characteristics of RC.

Beyond optimization, we extended RC frameworks to support online transfer learning and inference, enabling fast and energy-efficient adaptation to real-world scenarios. Our enhancements allowed **seamless online learning with only a 1% accuracy drop while using 66% less memory** in the worst case compared to baseline approaches. These contributions mark a step forward in making RC a scalable and adaptable alternative to computationally expensive deep learning models. Consequently, this approach enables easy access for new adopters and facilitates the research and development of RC technology.

Future work will focus on further improving RC's robustness in dynamic environments, exploring HP's impact on deeper and modular architectures, and integrating RC with hybrid AI paradigms to enhance its applicability in Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing. By addressing these aspects, we aim to position RC as a competitive, efficient, and sustainable alternative in the evolving AI landscape.

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